

Host Galaxy Based Supernova Classification

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ABSTRACT

Upcoming optical surveys such as the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope will discover supernovae at rates far out-pacing feasible spectroscopic classification. It is therefore critical that we optimize alternate classification methods using all available information. The use of host galaxy data for classification has not been well-developed, despite well-known trends between host galaxy properties and supernova types, and machine learning methods are well suited to this task of identifying complex trends. Using Pan-STARRS1 Medium-Deep Survey (PS1-MDS) images, we trained machine learning algorithms to predict supernovae types using solely contextual information. In particular, we present a random forest classifier using known host galaxy properties, and a convolutional neural network using host galaxy images. Classifying between types Ia, Ibc, II, IIc, and superluminous, we find the convolutional neural network performs significantly better than the random forest classifier. They achieve average accuracies per class of 63% and 47% respectively. The convolutional neural network performs similarly across most classes with accuracies above 50%, whereas the random forest struggles to classify types IIc and Ibc. Classifying between supernovae Ia and all other types, we achieve similar accuracy with both algorithms, with 70% in the random forest and 74% in the CNN. This is a significant improvement from existing host-galaxy based classification work (Foley and Mandel 2013). Future work includes combining our algorithms with photometric classification pipelines for optimized classification.

1. INTRODUCTION

Supernovae are traditionally classified according to their spectra. However, optical surveys are discovering supernovae at exponentially increasing rates with which spectroscopic follow-up will be unable to keep up. There is therefore an urgent need for alternative algorithms to classify the remaining supernovae. Much work has been done in developing photometric methods, for example Boone (2019); Lochner et al. (2016); Möller & de Boissière (2019); Muthukrishna et al. (2019); Pasquet et al. (2019); Villar et al. (2019). However, far less work has been done taking into account host galaxy information. This is despite known correlations between host galaxy properties and supernova

types. For example, core collapse types of supernovae generally come from massive, young stellar progenitors, and they are therefore less likely to occur in elliptical galaxies where there is little star formation. In contrast, Type Ias, having white dwarf progenitors, frequently occur in both star forming and non-star forming galaxies. [Foley & Mandel \(2013\)](#) create a classification algorithm to distinguish between Type Ia and core collapse supernova using direct correlations between individual properties of the host galaxy and the supernova type. However, this classification can be improved by taking into account the relationships between galaxy properties and more complicated correlations between combinations of galaxy properties and supernova types. Machine learning techniques are well suited to this purpose because of their ability to learn and extrapolate complex trends which may not be obvious to the human eye, and we do find it to be significantly more successful than their direct correlation method. Furthermore, host galaxy data also has value for classifying between different core-collapse types of supernovae, which we will make use of.

Our purpose here is to further develop the use of host galaxy data towards supernova classification, utilizing machine learning, motivated by the importance of optimizing non-spectroscopic galaxy classification through all available means. We train our algorithms using the Pan-STARRS medium-deep survey which has enough depth for us to detect hosts for a range of supernova types and redshifts. It furthermore has similar filter, depth, and cadence properties to the upcoming Large Synoptic Survey telescope, making our algorithm easily transferable to use with LSST data.

We first train a random forest classifier on known galaxy properties such as magnitude, ellipticity, and radius, which we extract from Pan-STARRS images surrounding the locations of our sample of spectroscopically classified supernovae. A random forest classifier uses an ensemble of decision trees which each classify based on a subset of galaxy properties, leading to a collective decision. Though this algorithm is more limited than the convolutional neural network we will also build, we develop it in order to get a sense of the extent to which known galaxy properties can tell us the types of supernovae in our sample. The success of the random forest shows us the minimum baseline we expect the convolutional neural network to perform and gives us an idea of how much the convolutional neural network is able to use non-human defined properties. The random forest is therefore useful as a baseline point of reference.

We then develop a convolutional neural network trained directly on host galaxy images. A convolutional neural network works by taking a filter matrix and convolving it with the input images, optimizing the filter matrix to best lead to accurate classification. It therefore has the advantage of being able to detect and make use of context properties which have not been noticed or defined by humans. We do find it to perform significantly better than the random forest for classifying between the 5 types.

This paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we introduce the Pan-STARRS dataset used to train our algorithms. In Section 3 we describe our methods, including the host galaxy detection and selection process in 3.1, the Random Forest Classifier in 3.2, and the Convolutional Neural Network in 3.3. In Section 4 we describe our results

in both classes, in classifying between the five types as well in classifying Type Ias vs. core collapse types. In Section 5 we compare our algorithm to the previous [Foley & Mandel \(2013\)](#), in Section 6 we discuss the limitations of our algorithms, and we conclude in Section 7.

2. DATA DESCRIPTION

Our data comes from the Pan-STARRS1 (PS1) wide-field survey telescope in Haleakala, Hawaii. The telescope has a primary mirror of diameter 1.8m and a 1.4 gigapixel camera (GPC1) with a 7.1 deg^2 field of view and a 0.258 arcsecond pixel scale, made up of 60 4800×4800 pixel detectors. The survey included g, r, i, z, and y broadband filters, though we only use the g, r, i, and z filter data has less depth and cadence frequency. Filter details can be found in [Stubbs et al. \(2010\)](#) and [Tonry et al. \(2012\)](#).

We used supernovae and host galaxy images from the Pan-STARRS Medium-Deep Survey (PS1-MDS, 2010-2014). This survey covered around 70 deg^2 in ten single-pointing fields, and it made up about 25% of Pan-STARRS observing time [Chambers et al. \(2016\)](#). Each filter excluding y_{P1} reached a 5σ depth of ≈ 23.3 magnitude per observation. In the y_{P1} filter, observations only reached a 5σ depth of ≈ 21.7 which is insufficient for our purposes, and therefore we do not use this filter.

From this survey, researchers found 5235 likely supernovae ([Jones et al. \(2017, 2018\)](#)) and spectroscopically classified over 500 them using the MMT 6.5-m, Magellan 6.5, and Gemini 8-m telescopes and the SNID software package [Blondin & Tonry \(2007\)](#). Those of Types Ia, IIP, and I SLSNe are published in [Jones et al. \(2017\)](#), [Sanders et al. \(2015\)](#), and [Lunnan et al. \(2018\)](#) respectively. We train our algorithm on 481 of these spectroscopically classified supernovae. (At the time of writing this paper, we were unable to access data for the remaining classified supernovae due to a computer disk failure.) Within our sample, 337 are of Type Ia, 19 are of Type Ibc, 88 are of Type II, 24 are of Type IIin, and 15 are superluminous. The original set of classified supernovae also included a few other rare types of transients in the survey, but not in sufficient quantities for us to be able to meaningfully include them in our classification algorithm.

We also use images of the areas surrounding the supernovae locations from the Medium Deep Survey to train our algorithms. The Pan-STARRS1 Image Processing Pipeline IPP; [Magnier et al. \(2016a,b\)](#); [Waters et al. \(2016\)](#) performed the reduction, astrometry, and stacking of the Medium Deep Survey images. See [Rest et al. \(2014\)](#), [Scolnic et al. \(2018\)](#), [Jones et al. \(2018\)](#) for further details of the analysis process.

The images from all years of the survey, excluding the year in which the supernova occurred, were aligned and stacked to generate deep images of the background only. For example, for a supernova occurring in 2011, our stack would include all images from 2009, 2010, 2012, 2013, and 2014. About 10% of our supernovae occur within the last half of December, so their galaxy images from the following year could contain some supernova light in them. We

were, however, unable to acquire stacks excluding only part of a year, and we need all available years in order to get sufficient depth. We furthermore did not want to discard any events because we are already limited by our small sample size. The small amount of contamination from supernova light is therefore a limitation to our work, though it occurs rarely enough that it does not prevent our algorithms from learning real trends.

It is possible for SNID to occasionally misclassify supernovae. Therefore we visually inspected the light curves for all samples of our smallest classes and verified that they were correctly classified, so we know our smallest samples are pure.

3. METHODS

3.1. *Host Detection*

Taking Pan-STARRS images of one square arc-minute surrounding the location of each classified supernova, we use `SEP` (Barbary (2016)), a Python library based on the `Source Extractor` software (Bertin & Arnouts (1996)), to detect host-galaxy candidates.

Though it is often clear from an image which galaxy is the host of a supernovae, at other times the host is more difficult to identify. At times the supernova is outside of the visible radius of its host, and multiple galaxies from different depths may all appear to be near the event location due to projection. Furthermore, at higher redshifts, the host may be too dim to detect in certain filters.

To ensure we are identifying the most likely host in ambiguous cases, we choose our host based on a formula from Bloom et al. (2002) to calculate the chance C_c that each galaxy is in the vicinity of the supernova by coincidence and therefore is not the host:

$$P_{cc} = 1 - e^{-\pi R_e^2 \sigma(\leq m)}.$$

R_e is the effective radius, given by

$$R_e = \sqrt{R^2 + 4R_h^2}.$$

R is the offset between the event and the center of the host candidate, and R_h is the radius of the host candidate. $\sigma(\leq m)$ is the density of galaxies brighter in magnitude than m , given by

$$\sigma = \frac{10^{0.33(m-24)-2.44}}{0.33 \log(10)}.$$

The galaxy with the lowest chance of coincidence was chosen as the host by default. However, if the supernova location fell outside of the object with the lowest chance coincidence, and different object(s) were found to have a photometric redshift matching the redshift of the event, the object with the lowest chance coincidence that also had a matching redshift was used. Any detected source in the image which was coincident with the location of a star identified in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey was excluded from host galaxy candidacy. Host galaxies were first chosen separately in each filter and then compared across filters. If different hosts were chosen in different filters, the host with the lowest chance of coincidence of all the filters was used in all filters. If no host could be found in any filter with chance coincidence lower than 0.02 or a matching redshift, default (average) data was used for that event as is described in the next section.

We also tested our algorithm on just the subset of supernovae which were located within a galaxy, in order to remove uncertainty about which galaxy was the host. We found that this did not noticeably change our results. We therefore incorporate the chance of coincidence formula and include supernovae which occur outside of their host in order to make our algorithm more broadly applicable, since by doing so we do not lose significant accuracy.

3.2. *Random Forest Classifier*

A random forest (RF) classifier (Breiman (2001)) is a machine learning algorithm which performs classification by developing a collection of decision trees. Each decision tree consists of a series of decisions to be made based on a value of the input, which in our case is properties of the host galaxy. The algorithm follows a path based on its input through the tree to a classification. The collection of trees, each trained on a subset of the values of the input, then vote to output a single type. Using a forest instead of a single tree improves accuracy and decreases the risk of overfitting, which is when the algorithm learns a useless, non-generalizable one-to-one relationship between inputs and outputs.

We used the `scikit-learn` python package to build our RF classifier. We used 200 decision trees in our algorithm, as we found this to be optimal for success. All other parameters were left to the `scikit-learn` default values.

We had significantly uneven sample sizes for different types of supernovae, with many more Type Ias than the other types. Training on uneven sample sizes tends to make algorithms biased towards classifying inputs as the more common types, since by doing so they could increase their overall accuracy. To avoid this problem, we used Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE, Chawla et al. (2002)) to create synthetic data, meaning additional artificial inputs which resemble the real inputs, to add to the less common classes. SMOTE randomly creates artificial data corresponding to points in the input matrix space which fall on the line segments which would connect the real input points in the input matrix space; basically this results in additional inputs which are like weighted averages of

Figure 1. Examples of host galaxy identification. Purple triangle marks location where the supernova occurred. Green oval marks the most likely host calculated from the chance coincidence. Objects circled in blue are stars identified using SDSS, all other objects are in red.

the original inputs. Since Type Ia is our largest class, we over-sampled the other classes to match the size of our Type Ia sample.

We extract the following galaxy properties from the PS1-MDS images to form the inputs for the RF classifier: apparent and absolute magnitude, ellipticity, distance between supernova location and host center, separation/ \sqrt{area} , pixel rank, and the chance of coincidence of the most likely host. Pixel rank was used as a measure of whether the event happened in a brighter or dimmer part of galaxy, which can be an indicator of whether the supernova occurred in a star-forming region of the galaxy. Pixel rank was calculated as the percent of host galaxy pixels which were dimmer than the pixel corresponding to the event location if the event was located within the host object, and 0 otherwise. Properties were calculated separately for each filter, the values from all four filters were used. G,r,i, and z magnitudes are therefore all included.

If, for a specific filter no object could be detected at the location of the final chosen most likely host, we copied over the data from the filter with the lowest chance of coincidence for the most likely host, except for the magnitude which was calculated by photometry on that area. For supernovae where no likely host could be detected to a 3σ threshold in any of our filter bands, we used the average values of the entire sample, as is literature standard, and the image’s limiting magnitude + 1 was used for the magnitude.

3.3. Convolutional Neural Network

We also built a convolutional neural network (CNN), a type of a deep neural network which works well for classification based on images. CNNs work by taking an initially-random filter matrix, convolving it with the input image, and passing on the output matrix to the next layer of the neural network. After passing through several convolution layers, the resulting values are passed to a fully connected neural network. Here, each layer consists of nodes which each take all the outputs of the previous layer, multiply them by adjustable weights, pass their sum through a non-linear function and output the result to the next layer. As it is trained, the algorithm then optimizes the filter matrices and weights in order to most accurately classify the inputs it receives.

We trained our cnn directly on the PS1-MDS images of the area surrounding the location where each supernova occurred. Unlike our RF algorithm, in which potentially valuable information contained in the images is lost in the extraction process, the CNN takes in the entire image directly and therefore can make use of potentially complex host galaxy properties and host-event correlations, even those which we might not think of.

In our initial input, each pixel containing 6 values: the $g_{P1}r_{P1}i_{P1}z_{P1}$ values, the event redshift, and a value set to $1 - C_c$, the chance coincidence of the most-likely host galaxy if the pixels was part of the most likely host, and 0 otherwise.

For the filter matrices, we use 2 dimensional 3 by 3 convolution filters which are convolved across each layer of pixel values. In the architecture we found to work well, there are three convolution layers, each followed by a rectified linear unit (relu, [Nair & Hinton \(2010\)](#)) activation layer which zeros out negative values, and then a pooling layer, which reduces the output by taking the average of each 2x2 square of values. This is followed by an additional pooling layer taking the average of every 5x5 square of values. It then ends with two fully connected layers of neurons, which each take the dot product of its inputs and its weights vector, pass the output through a non-linear activation function (Softmax [Jang et al. \(2016\)](#)), and then output the result. The final output of the last fully connected layer corresponds to the prediction of the supernova type. The algorithm then optimizes the filter matrices as well as the neuron weight to maximize classification accuracy. It does this by Adam optimization ([Kingma & Ba \(2014\)](#)) with learning rate 5×10^{-3} . We trained our data on batches of size 50 samples at a time, for 200 epochs.

When training the algorithm, we augmented our training set in order to balance our sample sizes for each type to prevent our algorithm from developing biases due to uneven sample sizes. We did this by adding additional randomly rotated and reflected copies of the less common classes from within the same training set. We then cropped all the images from 240×240 pixels to 160×160 pixels after rotation to eliminate empty corners. The result represents 0.67×0.67 arcminutes.

We evaluated the success of our algorithm using K-fold validation: We split our sample into 15 subsets, evenly dividing each of our types. For each of the 15 subsets, we trained an algorithm on the other 14 subsets and then tested the success of the algorithm on the subset which had been left out.

Figure 2. Convolutional Neural Network. The input consists of pixel arrays of the square surrounding the event location. Each pixel containing 6 values: the $g_{P_1} r_{P_1} i_{P_1} z_{P_1}$ values, the event redshift, and a value set to $1 - C_c$, the chance coincidence of the most-likely host galaxy if the pixels was part of the most likely host, and 0 otherwise. A filter matrix is then convolved with the inputs in convolution layers. Pooling layers decrease the size by taking the average value of square pools. These are followed by fully connected layers, which lead to a classification. The filter matrices and the weights of the fully connected layer nodes are optimized during training so as to best map inputs to classifications.

4. RESULTS

4.1. *RF results*

The random forest classifier, using only known galaxy properties, serves as a baseline for machine learning host galaxy based classification. With the random forest classifier, we were able to achieve an average accuracy per class of 0.47, which is significantly better than random which would yield 20%. Figure 4 shows our confusion matrix, a visualization of our success and mis-classification rates for each of the types. The random forest classifier has significant success in classifying Type Ia and superluminous supernovae, with success rates of 74% and 78% respectively, but it struggles to classify Types Ibc and IIn, achieving only 25% and 11% accuracy in those categories. This is because it tends to misclassify Type IIns as Type Ias, and Type Ibc as Type IIs.

We also separately trained it to classify just between Type Ia and other, and achieved 70% accuracy with this. See 6 for the confusion matrix.

The *feature importances* of a RF are a metric of how significant features of the input are to the algorithm for classification, relative to one another; features of higher importance were more heavily used in determining the output. Figure 3 shows a bar graph of our feature importances. We can see that several properties, such as separation and area, were less important to the classifier than a random number meaning, they were unuseful for classification. Radius (Kron Rad), apparent magnitude (Kron Mag), and chance coincidence are the most important features.

4.2. *CNN results*

With the convolutional neural network, we achieve an average accuracy per class of 63%, a significant improvement over the random forest. We see an improvement in accuracy over the random forest in all classes except Type Ia. Also, we see no major mis-classification tendencies, with the algorithm classifying each type correctly more often than not. The improvement of the CNN over the RF classifier demonstrates that there is useful information in host galaxy properties other than the commonly defined ones used in our random forest, and the the CNN is effective at picking these up.

4.3. *Ia vs. Other*

We also separately trained our algorithms to classify between Type Ias and all other types, since this is a useful classification for cosmological research. We found similar success rates in both algorithms, with 70% in the random forest and 74% in the CNN. We suspect that the reason the CNN does not improve significantly over the RF is that it is reaching the limits of galaxy-based classification, since host galaxies properties do not completely determine the supernova type. Our accuracy is significantly better than previous host galaxy based classification (see Section 5 for comparison).

5. COMPARISON TO PREVIOUS HOST-GALAXY BASED CLASSIFICATION

Figure 3. Feature Importances from RF Classifier. The *feature importances* are a metric of how significant features of the input are to the algorithm for classification, relative to one another; features of higher importance were more heavily used in determining the output. Importance values are relative and useful only for comparison with one another. For each feature, the four bars represent the importance of the feature in the input corresponding to the *g*, *r*, *i*, *z* filters from left to right. Chosen host galaxy locations were cross-referenced between filters to ensure that the same host was chosen in all filters, though magnitudes, radii, etc. may still vary between filters. The horizontal dashed line is the feature importance of a random value for comparison. We can see that several properties, such as separation and area, were less important than the random number meaning they were unuseful for classification. Radius (Kron Rad), apparent magnitude (Kron Mag), and chance coincidence are the most important features.

In their *galsnid* classification algorithm, [Foley & Mandel \(2013\)](#) use direct correlations between individual host-galaxy properties and supernova types to predict whether a supernova is of Type Ia or a core collapse type. Their algorithm is trained on LOSS survey data [Leaman et al. \(2011\)](#).

Both *galsnid* and our random forest classifier include in their input pixel rank, and offset. *Galsnid* additionally takes in *K* band magnitude and $B_0 - K$ color. We instead use *griz* magnitudes, from which the algorithm should be able to learn any colors which are combinations of those bands. Though Foley and Mandel use host galaxy morphology as one of their inputs, our sample is of generally higher redshifts than theirs, and therefore do not have the resolution to morphologically classify the galaxies in our sample. However, we do include magnitude and we expect the algorithm to learn color, which should give it some information about morphology.

Figure 4. Random Forest Classifier Confusion Matrix showing success and misclassifications. Rows correspond to actual types and columns correspond to classifier predicted types. Numbered boxes indicate the fraction of row type which were classified as column type, e.g. 11% of SLSNe were misclassified as SNIa.

Our algorithm is an improvement from [Foley & Mandel \(2013\)](#) firstly by extending to also classify between core collapse types of supernovae. Furthermore, their algorithm assumes all galaxy properties are uncorrelated, and they suggest that improvement could be made by taking into account correlations. Our random forest algorithm implements this improvement, as it makes no assumptions about relationships between properties or lack thereof. Machine learning is furthermore capable of detecting relationships between complex combinations of inputs and the corresponding outputs, giving it further advantage over the use of direct correlations.

The CNN receives even more complete information, allowing it to learn even more complicated correlations, since it receives the images themselves. It therefore has an advantage over both the random forest classifier and *galsnid* in that it can make use of galaxy properties which have not been noticed or defined by humans. This likely contributes to its higher success rate.

Foley and Mandel used a Figure of Merit (FoM) from [Kessler et al. \(2010\)](#) to quantify their success. It is given by efficiency times psuedopurity:

$$FoM = \epsilon_{Ia} \times PP_{Ia}$$

Figure 5. Convolutional Neural Network Confusion Matrix.

Figure 6. Random Forest Confusion Matrix for Type Ia vs. Core Collapse.

where efficiency is

$$\epsilon_{Ia} = N_{Ia}^{Sub} / N_{Ia}^{Tot}$$

Figure 7. Convolutional Neural Network Confusion Matrix for Type Ia vs. Core Collapse.

with N_{Ia}^{Tot} being the actual number of Type Ia supernova in the sample, N_{Ia}^{Sub} being the number of Type Ia supernova which get correctly classified as Type Ia. Pseudopurity is given by

$$PP_{Ia} = \frac{N_{Ia}^{Sub}}{N_{Ia}^{Sub} + 5N_{Non-Ia}^{Sub}}$$

with N_{Non-Ia}^{Sub} being the number of non-Ia supernova incorrectly classified as Type Ias. By adjusting their classification weighting, they achieve a maximum FoM of 0.27 when weighting heavily towards classification as core collapse. We achieved FoM of 0.46 with close to neutral weighting. This is a significant improvement from *galsnid*, likely due to the differences discussed earlier in this section. Our algorithm probably peaks near neutral weighting because it was trained to optimize at neutral weighting whereas *galsnid* uses only direct correlations.

6. LIMITATIONS

WE use redshift in both of our classificatino algorithms. For the RF, this enables us to calculate absolute magnitudes and projected offsets, which in turn should enable the algorithm to pick up on trends between true physical galaxy properties and supernova types. For the data set we used to train the algorithms, we had access to the spectroscopically derived redshift of each supernova. Though we typically will not have spectroscopic redshifts for unclassified supernova or their hosts from future surveys, in LSST we will have access to photometric redshifts for all galaxies brighter than 27.5 magnitude, which we will be able to use instead. Galaxies brighter than 25.3 magnitude having an expected root-mean-square scatter $\sigma_z/(1+z) \lesssim 0.05$. Fewer than 10% of redshifts are expected to be 3σ outliers. The additional uncertainty of photometric redshifts should not be a limiting factor for our algorithms.

Figure 8. Comparison with [Foley & Mandel \(2013\)](#).

Though our use of redshift would hypothetically inhibit our ability to classify events deeper than the training set, our algorithms would probably not be useful on such events anyway since the host galaxies at such high redshifts would not be well visible in images.

Another limitation to our algorithms is that they can only classify between the five types. They could easily be extended through retraining on a data set including other types, which can be done quickly and easily. They would still, however, be unable to identify new and unforeseen classes. Our classifying between 5 types is still much better than the limited previous classification between only Ia and core collapse.

We do not take into account any biases that may exist in our spectroscopically classified training set. Though this could be addressed in the random forest classifiers by adjusting weighting within the training set, there is no clear solution for our convolutional neural network.

Our classification likely creates biased samples of each of the supernova types if correlations exist between properties of supernova of a given type and their host galaxy. For example, Type Ias occurring in star-forming galaxies could have differences in typical properties from Type Ias occurring in quenched galaxies. If using sets of supernova created using our algorithms, one would need to be mindful of biases caused by the nature of our classification.

Clearly, samples created using our algorithm should not be used to investigate correlations between supernovae and host galaxies.

We are also limited by our small sample size for certain classes, especially the superluminous supernovae. This makes it difficult for our algorithms to learn trends. This limitation should be eliminated once a significant number of supernovae have been discovered by LSST and classified, creating larger samples at high redshifts.

We furthermore face the inherent physical limitations of classifying supernovae using only contextual information. The context of a supernova does not completely determine its type. Even if perfectly using all available contextual information, it would still be impossible for us to reach 100% accuracy. This can be partially addressed by combining our algorithm with photometric methods, which is an important future direction for our algorithm. Our classification methods should be able to significantly improve photometric methods especially early in the supernova, when photometric datapoints are limited.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Optimizing non-spectroscopic methods of supernova classification is currently important, as the rate of supernova discovery increases beyond the capacities of spectroscopic classification. It is well-known that supernova types correlate with various host galaxy properties. We develop two machine learning algorithms to classify supernova solely based on contextual data. To take advantage of these correlations, we train our algorithms on 481 spectroscopically classified supernova from the Pan-STARRS Medium-Deep Survey. Our first algorithm is a random forest classifier, which we train on extracted host galaxy properties including magnitude, ellipticity, offset between host galaxy and supernova location, and others. We use SMOTE resampling to balance the sample sizes of each type. This algorithm achieves an average accuracy per class of 47%, but with significantly less accuracy in classifying types II_n and Ib_c. It serves as a baseline with which to compare our second and more successful algorithm, a convolutional neural network. The CNN is trained directly on PS1-MDS images of the area surrounding the supernova, as well as redshift and a mask conveying the most likely host and its chance of coincidence. It uses rotations and reflections to balance the sample sizes of each type. It achieves a significant average accuracy per class of 63%, performing well on across all classes. Our algorithm is the first that we are aware of to use contextual data to classify between all 5 types of supernovae, and it a significant improvement from of previous host-galaxy based Ia versus core collapse supernova classification [Foley & Mandel \(2013\)](#). Future directions include combination with photometric classification methods.

Software: Astropy ([Price-Whelan et al. \(2018\)](#)), Keras ([Chollet et al. \(2015\)](#)), Matplotlib ([Hunter \(2007\)](#)), NumPy ([Van Der Walt et al. \(2011\)](#)), Pandas ([McKinney \(2010\)](#)), Scipy ([Oliphant \(2007\)](#)), Scikit-learn ([Pedregosa et al. \(2011\)](#)), SEP ([Barbary \(2016\)](#)), Bertin & Arnouts ([1996](#)), Tensorflow ([Abadi et al. \(2015\)](#))

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